

NAVIGATING LIBRARY RESOURCES: A STUDY OF ACQUISITION AND MANAGEMENT AT THE UNIVERSITY OF UYO

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Abstract: University libraries serve as vital catalysts for fostering effective and efficient learning, teaching, and research within the academic milieu. In this context, libraries assume a pivotal role in nurturing independent, knowledgeable graduates who are poised to contribute to an educated society. As Mohammed (2010) aptly suggests, libraries, as the driving force behind societal education, play a crucial part in the cultivation of such self-determined individuals. Notably, the acquisition of information resources is indispensable to the academic pursuits of students, lecturers, and researchers, ensuring that they successfully achieve their educational goals in a timely manner.

However, the value of information resources acquisition hinges on the effectiveness of their management. Management is the systematic process of steering an organization towards its objectives, making the most of both human and non-human resources while maintaining a clear vision of organizational goals. It encompasses several facets, including planning, staffing, reporting, and budgeting, all aimed at judiciously procuring and maintaining information resources within the library. Planning, in particular, is instrumental in determining which information resources to acquire, estimating the resources required, and formulating strategies for their effective management.

One crucial aspect of resource augmentation in university libraries is the receipt of donations and gifts, freely provided by individuals or corporate entities. These contributions are intended to enrich the library's resource base and can manifest in various forms, including printed materials such as books and journals, audio-visual assets like computers and video tapes, and even financial support. Effective management of these donations and gifts is imperative for their optimal utilization and impact.

Resource sharing, on the other hand, is a collaborative concept wherein two or more libraries form agreements to pool their resources, facilitating the exchange of information resources. These agreements typically stipulate the number of books to be shared and the specific duration for which they can be borrowed, renewed, or returned. Such cooperative initiatives are essential for ensuring the efficient and sustainable management of information resources in university libraries.

This paper delves into the critical interplay between information resources, their acquisition, and effective management within university libraries. It underscores the importance of proper planning, donations, and resource sharing in maximizing the utility of these resources for the benefit of the academic community.

Keywords: University libraries, information resources, resource management, donations, resource sharing.

1.1 Introduction

The purpose for the existence of a university library is to enhance effective and efficient learning, teaching and research in an academic environment. In the process of learning, teaching and research, libraries in the universities facilitate self-determining graduates for a knowledgeable society. Mohammed (2010) posited that the library which is the driving force for making the society to be educated plays vital roles in enhancing the graduation of these self-determining graduates. It is worthy to note that without the acquisition of information resources, students, lecturers and researchers will not be able to complete their academic endeavors successfully and as at when due. However, the acquisition of these information resources becomes useless without its effective management. Management is the process of reaching organizational goals, working with human and non-human resources with a clear picture of the organizational objectives in view. It entails planning, staffing, reporting and budgeting for information resources to be purchased into the library. Planning helps in

ensuring which information resources is to be purchased, its estimation and resources required in order to achieve its effective management. Donation/gifts are freewill information resources given to the library by individuals or co-operate bodies. Gifts/donations are made to enrich library resources. These resources (donations/gift) could be in form of print resources like books and journals, audio-visual materials like computers, videos tapes and even financial supports. Resource sharing is an idea or understanding between two or more libraries to come together in order to share their resources through the provision of information resources. In that respect, an agreement is usually reached and signed between resource sharing libraries, especially in terms of the number of books to be shared and the specific period they could either be returned or renewed for effective management of information resources.

Legal deposit is another method of acquiring information resources into the library. According to Wilkinson and Lewis (2009) legal deposits is legal requirement that a person or group submit copies of their publications to be repository, usually a Legal deposit is a statutory obligation that requires publishers who publish materials, including digital content, to deposit a copy or copies of their publications in specified national and regional repositories within the context of national legal deposit legislation.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The whole world is in an information age with the growth of information resources in a geometrical progression, and acquiring information resources is an important exercise for libraries despite the prophecies of vanishing print collections, and emergence of the digital paradigm (Carr, 2007). Also, it is an established fact that providing information resources needed by users is the main reason for the existence of libraries and librarians. However, it is sad to say that, based on consistent review of the bibliographic data, need for frequent information resources update in the University of Uyo Library and a close discussion with the librarians, has shown that, the acquisition process is not actually well ordered. Some librarians are of the opinion that acquisition process has nothing to do with effective management of the information resources while others are of the opinion that the library does not consider the management variables for effective collection development. These in turn affects the management of the information resources as to providing a functional collection development in the library; thereby creating problems to the library management. These problems have raised varied questions such as these: could poor resource purchase, resource donations/gifts, resource sharing, legal deposit or poor funding bring about ineffective moangement of library resources? If acquisition variables are properly considered then, it is likely that there should be no problem in management of information resources in the University of Uyo library. Hence, this study therefore seeks to examine the acquisition variables and how it relates to effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study was to investigate the relationship between the acquisition variables and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the relationship between resource purchase and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library.
2. Examine the relationship between resource donation/gifts and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library.
3. Ascertain the relationship between resource sharing and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library.
4. Examine the relationship between legal deposits and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the relationship between resource purchase and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library?
2. What is the relationship between resource donation/gifts and effective management of Uyo library?
3. What is the relationship between resource sharing and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library?
4. What is the relationship between legal deposit and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between resource purchase and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library?
2. There is no significant relationship between resource donation/gifts and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library?
3. There is no significant relationship between resource sharing and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library?
4. There is no significant relationship between legal deposit and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library?

2.1 Literature Review

This chapter reviewed related literature on acquisition variables and effective management of information resources. The review of literature considered the acquisition variables and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library. The review led to the understanding of the concept of acquisition as purchase, resources sharing, gifts and donation and legal deposit. These acquisition variables are seen to significantly influence effective management of information resources in the university library. The important of information resource acquisition with views of effective management of the acquired information resources is emphasized. This has made it clear that there is a gap existing in acquisition variables and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library. Therefore, this research seeks to fill this gap in knowledge. Library material is purchased in a range of formats, as appropriate and as advised by the acquisition librarian. All acquisition procedures are carried out on a best value for money basis. Amen (2008) asserted that a range of library suppliers are used to ensure the best available possible service and contractual terms for effective management of information resources. The library may also enter into collaborative agreements with other institutions to acquire material that is beneficial to the University through effective management. There may be a number of resources for such an agreement. Sivadas (2012) reported that “approval plan blanket order, standing order and firm order” are the ways in which purchase may be performed to maintain effective management of information resources. He also suggested that a combination of two or more methods may be used. Acquisition in any library entails the actual procurement of the information resources into the library and it requires effective management. Horava (2005) reported that acquisition of information resources into the academic library is focused on satisfying the information need of the university’s population. In order to achieve its aims, the library actively seeks and encourages the full participation of members of the university, most particularly, academic and research staff, in the selection of information resources into the library. This addition could be done through purchase, gifts/donations, resource sharing and legal deposit. According to Cassell (2009), purchase of information resources could be done in two ways, by direct order or by purchase. Direct purchase is the situation in which the librarian physically purchases the

information resources needed. In this case, the librarian has direct and immediate opportunity of assessing the bibliographical contents and ensuring the quick arrival of the resources to the library. By order, the librarian requests, through orders, the supply of needed information resources from a particular book vendor, publisher or through an agent. In Nigeria, many libraries have benefited from donation/gifts. They come from individuals, like “Late Chief Nyong Essien” who donated his personal files together with other information resources to the University of Uyo Library. It may also come from establishment/organizations such as the United Nations, Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), British Council, World Health Organization (WHO), United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund (UNICEF), United State Agency for International Development (USAID) among others. All libraries have guidelines as to what gifts will be accepted and what gifts will not be accepted into their collections, based on their collection development policy. Hence such gift materials must meet the same standards or selection criteria used for materials purchased for their collections. It is often easier to say what will not be accepted rather than what be accepted. Khurshid (2010) stated that a library, as an exception, may accept for its collections objects of nonlibrary character. In order to protect the library in the future, a written justification should be prepared relating the compelling circumstances involved and offering plans for custody in the library. Such recommendation should be approved in writing by the library director or another authorized individual. Many gifts may duplicate materials already owned by the library or may be out of date or out-of-scope for the collection. Resource sharing is a mutual agreement between libraries to exchange resources. Each library gives its own materials to other participating libraries and also receives same from them. Nwalo (2008) also defined resource sharing as a formal arrangement by a group of organizations that have common interests, to pull their material and human resources together so as to meet clientele needs much more than they could have done if they were to depend on individual efforts. At inception, inter-library lending constituted the major aspect of resource sharing as at today, it embraces many more activities. According to Ogum (2004), the types of sharing including interlibrary loans, joint acquisition, central cataloguing, exchange of library materials, computerized cataloguing schemes, awareness services and joint storage of materials.

Resource sharing makes information available at low cost and consequently reduces frustration of information users, exchange of collections, equipment, manpower and experience.

It makes libraries richer and more productive and aids effective management of information resources. Tahira and Ameen (2011) noted that, resource sharing is a process by which one library benefit from another. This process previously was regarded as inter-library. For resource sharing to be carried out successfully there must be a viable report system for effective management of the shared information resources. According to Mellon (2008), legal deposit is a legal obligation that requires publishers to deposit a copy (or copies) of their publications within a specified period of time in a designated national institution. The institution is usually a library, and must include the National Library. The national archive should be maintained by a legal requirement of depositing published information resources has been well established for almost four centuries. Legal deposit does not usually apply to unpublished works or original works of art, but increasingly includes published audio-visual and electronic materials. Legal deposit helps to ensure that the published record of human memory, creativity and discovery are acquired by the nation so that it can be preserved and made available to future generations. According to Cassell (2009), information resource deposited under the legal deposit laws are a valuable resource to publishers themselves for accessing their own historical output in years to come, it also serve as a current preservation techniques and finding aids are applied to the deposited materials under the professional care of the libraries where these information resources are kept. According to Feather (2007), there are guidelines for legal deposit legislation. The legal deposit is common with national libraries as it were, to maintain effective management of deposited information

resources. Some academic libraries like University of Ibadan, University of Lagos, University of Nigeria, Ahmadu Bello University libraries enjoy this privilege. The requirement is mostly limited to information resources such as books and periodicals. The number of copies varies depending on the law. Typically, the national library is one of the repositories for these copies.

3.1 Research Design/Population/Sampling and Sampling Technique

This study adopted the descriptive survey design because the study intend to collect and present data to give a clear picture of acquisition variables and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library. The population of the study consisted of all academic librarians numbering (28) in the University Library. Census sampling techniques was used to select the sample size, the technique was found appropriate since the sample size was small. Castells (2000) acclaimed that, census sampling technique involves selecting subjects of units in a population to represent all units in a population of interest.

3.1.1 Procedure for Data Collection

Twenty-four copies of the instrument was administered to the respondent. The instrument was administered and collected on the spot because the population was small and of manageable size.

3.1.2 Method of Data Analysis

Research questions were answered using percentages while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at .05 level of significance.

4.1 Analysis of Data and Discussion of Findings

The result of data analysis are presented and discussed below:

4.1.1 Research Question 1: What is the relationship between resource purchase and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library?

Table 1: Percentages of respondents' responses on Resource purchase and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library

S/N	Resource purchase and effective management of information resources	SA %	A %	D %	SD %
1	The library purchase information resources in preparation for accreditation only	6(25)	11(45.8)	6(25)	1(4.2)
2	Information resources are purchased in the library regularly	3(12.5)	13(54.2)	6(25)	2(8.3)
3	All fields of study are given equal attention during purchase	3(12.5)	6(25)	4(16.6)	11(45.8)
4	The library management does not have enough funds for the purchase of information materials	10(41.7)	9(37.5)	2(8.33)	3(12.5)
5	The library management does not have enough funds for the purchase of information materials	5(20.8)	14(58.3)	0(0)	5(20.8)

N/B: The numbers in bracket indicates the percentage

The entries in Table 1 show the respondents' responses to the purchase variable of acquisition. The observed figures and their relative percentages shows that most of the library staff are aware that the library management does not have enough funds for the purchase of information resources; which is the pre-requisite for the availability of the needed information resources in the University library.

4.1.2 Research Question Two: What is the relationship between resource gift/donation and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library?

Table 2: Percentages of respondents' responses on resource donation/gifts and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo Library

S/N	Gifts and effective management of information resources	SA %	A %	D %	SD %
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1	The library encourages gift of information resources	11(45.8)	9(37.5)	4(16.7)	0(0)
2	Individuals and cooperate bodies regularly gives to the library	4(16.7)	4(16.7)	8(33.3)	8(33.3)
3	Books acquired through gifts accounts for a greater percent of the library collection	5(20.8)	5(20.8)	7(29.2)	7(29.2)
4	Information resources given to the library are found useful to users	6(25)	5(20.8)	9(37.5)	4(16.7)
5	Information resources given to the library are found obsolete within a short period of time	5(20.8)	5(20.8)	8(33.3)	6(25)

N/B: The numbers in bracket indicates the percentage

The data on Table 2 shows the respondents' responses to the resource donations variables of acquisition on effective management of information resources. The observed figures and their relative percentages shows that most of the library staff are aware that library management donates and receives gifts of information resources which is the imperative for the availability of needed information resources in the University library.

4.1.3 Research Question Three: What is the relationship between resource sharing and effective management of information resource in the university OF Uyo library?

Table 3: Percentages of respondents' responses on resource sharing and effective Management of information Resource in the University of Uyo library

S/N	Resource sharing and effective management of information resource	SA %	A %	D %	SD %
1	The library is in consortia with other libraries for information resources	5(20.8)	4(16.7)	15(62.8)	0(0)
2	There is need for resource sharing in the library	15(62.8)	5(20.8)	0(0)	4(16.7)
3	Shortage of funds prompt library management to embark on resource sharing	5(20.8)	5(20.8)	4(16.7)	6(25)
4	Information resources acquired through consortia satisfies the users information needs	0(0)	20(83.3)	0(0)	4(16.7)
5	Resources sharing is not as effective as it was before now	12(50)	9(37.5)	3(12.5)	0(0)

N/B: The numbers in bracket indicate the percentage

The data on Table 3 shows the respondents' responses to the resource sharing variable of acquisition on effective management of information resources. The observed figures and their relative percentages shows that most of the library staff are aware that the management of the University library share information resources with libraries of other affiliating institutions. This resource sharing is a pre-requisite for effective management of information resources in University of Uyo library.

4.1.4 Research Question Four: What is the relationship between legal deposit and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library?

Table 4: Percentages of respondents' responses on legal deposit and effective Management of information Resource in the University of Uyo library

S/N	Legal deposit and effective management of information resources	SA %	A %	D %	SD %
1	My library is a legal depository center	4(16.7)	5(20.8)	15(62.8)	0(0)
2	Legally Deposited information resource are found useful to users	5(20.8)	0(0)	15(62.8)	4(16.7)

3	Legal Deposit has helped to boost library collection	9(37.5)	4(16.7)	5(20.8)	6(25)
4	Deposited books accounts for greater percent of library collection	4(16.7)	0(0)	0(0)	20(83.3)
5	Legal deposit aids users in specific fields	9(37.5)	3(12.5)	12(50)	0(0)

N/B: The numbers in bracket indicate the percentage.

The data on Table 4 shows the respondents' responses to the legal deposit variable of acquisition. The observed figures and their relative percentages show that most of the library staff are not aware of the roles legal deposit play in the management of information resources. This could be justified as there are insignificant cases of legal deposits of information resource in the University of Uyo library.

Table 5: Percentages of respondents' responses on the dependent variable of effective management of information Resource in the University of Uyo library

S/N	Management of library resources	SA %	A %	D %	SD %
1	Information resources purchased aids in effective management of users	14(58.3)	6(25)	4(16.7)	0(0)
2	Gift promotes effective management of information resources	10(41.7)	10(41.7)	0(0)	4(16.7)
3	Resources sharing brings about effective management of information resources	9(37.5)	10(41.7)	5(20.8)	0(0)
4	Effective management of library resources is achieved through legal deposit	6(25)	0(0)	5(20.8)	13(54.2)

N/B: The numbers in bracket indicates the percentage

The data on Table 5 shows the respondents' responses to the dependent variable of acquisition and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library. The observed figures and their relative percentages shows that most academic library staff knows that resource purchase, resources gift/donation and resource sharing are very important for effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between resource purchase and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

Table 6: Summary of PPMC analysis of data on relationship between resource purchase and effective

management of information resources in the University of Uyo library					
Variables	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	r-value	r-crit
Resource purchase (X)	327	4563			
Effective management of information resources (Y)	314	4186	4332	0.59 ^S	0.40

S = Significant at .05 level; df = 22; N = 24; critical r-value = 0.40

The result in the Table 6 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.59 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.40 at .05 level of significance with 24 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between resource purchase and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between resource donation and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

Table 7: Summary of PPMC analysis of data on relationship between resource donation and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library

Variables	r-value	r-crit	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	ΣY	ΣY^2
Resource gift/donation (X)	291	3669					
Effective management of information resources (Y)	0.60 ^S	0.40	314	4186	3869		

S = Significant at .05 level; df = 22; N = 24; critical r-value = 0.40

The result in the Table 7 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.60 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.40 at .05 level of significance with 24 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between resource donation/gifts and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

4.2.3 Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between resource sharing and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

Table 8: Summary of PPMC analysis of data on relationship between resource sharing and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library

Variables	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	r-value	r-crit
Resource sharing (X)	339	4881			
Effective management of information resources (Y)	314	4186	4488	0.59 ^S	0.40

S = Significant at .05 level; df = 22; N = 24; critical r-value = 0.40

The result in the Table 8 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.51 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.40 at .05 level of significance with 24 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between resource sharing and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

4.2.4 Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between legal deposit and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

Table 9: Summary of PPMC analysis of data on relationship between legal deposit and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library

Variables	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	r-value	r-crit
Legal deposit (X)	369	5765			
Effective management of information resources (Y)	314	4186	4800	0.27 ^S	0.40

S = Significant at .05 level; df = 22; N = 24; critical r-value = 0.40

The result in the Table 9 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.27 is less than the critical r-value of 0.40 at .05 level of significance with 24 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis was retained.

This implies that there is no significant relationship between legal deposit and effective management of information resources in the University of Uyo library.

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that university library is established to serve the information needs of students, researchers, lecturers, and the entire university community. This information needs is serviced through purchase, donation/gifts, resource sharing and legal deposit of the information resources as established by the research. As a result of this, effective management of the information resources should be enhanced to ensure the satisfaction of the information needs of the users

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. More information resources should be purchased and should be manned by professionals.
2. The library should make it clear as a matter of policy of what information resources to be accepted as gifts for effective management of the resources.
3. Resource sharing be enhanced to boost the collections of the library.
4. The management of the library should encourage deposit of publications by all authors in the University of Uyo, to the library so as to boost information resource acquired through legal deposit.

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